

ROLE OF *MEDHYA RASAYANA* IN PSYCHOLOGICAL FUNCTIONING AND RELATED DISORDERS

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ABSTRACT

The *Tridosha* needs to be in balance for optimal *Medha* or cognitive function. When *Vata* and *Kapha* are in harmony, cognitive function will be enhanced through strong memory and retention. The properties of *Pitta* enhance sharpness, analytical ability and intelligence quotient. Thus, Ayurvedic practitioners have identified several single drug formulations and a variety of compound formulations for enhancing and maintaining cognitive function through the balance of *Tridosha*. In this regards Ayurveda described specific *Medhya Rasayanans* such as; *Mandukaparni Swarasa*, *Yastimadhu Churna*, *Guduchi Swarasa* and *Shankhapushpi Kalka*. *Medhya Rasayanans* are said to possess the qualities of restorative, rejuvenating and anxiolytic properties. They also improve strength, *Agni*, luster, quality of voice and improve cognitive ability. By enhancing *Dhi*, *Dhriti* and *Smriti*, the use of *Medhya Rasayanans* significantly contributes to maintaining mental health, preventing cognitive dysfunction, and assisting in the management of all forms of mental illness regardless of age.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, *Medha*, *Rasayanans*, *Dhriti*, *Smriti*.

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, the word *Medha* refers to intelligence, ability to comprehend and ability to retain memories. The concept of *Medhya* is broad and includes three interdependent aspects of mental function *Dhi*, *Dhriti* and *Smriti*. The well being of mental functioning depend upon these mental functions and use of *Medhya Rasayana* helps significantly in this regards. *Medhya Rasayana* may be acquired by people who are otherwise healthy to increase their cognitive functioning, as well as by people who are suffering from neurological and/or psychiatric conditions that result in impaired cognitive functioning, particularly memory loss and cognitive deficits.^[1-4]

Medhya Rasayana can also be correlated with modern-day "nootropic" medications, which acts as cognitive enhancers, help to improve brain function through the stimulation of neuronal growth; by enhancing cerebral oxygenation; and by optimizing the activity of

neurotransmitters. The effects of *Rajasika Ahara*, along with factors that adversely affect the *Dhriti* of the *Manas*, include psychological factors such as over-thinking, failure to achieve goals, lack of mental stability and low self-esteem, etc.

The principal *Medhya Rasayana* formulations identified in ancient text includes four medicines; *Mandukaparni Swarasa*, *Yastimadhu Churna*, *Guduchi Swarasa* and *Shankhapushpi Kalka*. The major *Medhyas* herbs used in Ayurvedic practices includes *Brahmi*, *Vacha*, *Jyotishmati*, *Ashwagandha* and *Jatamamsi*. *Medhya Rasayanans* can be categorized into two categories (**Figure 1**), first one is cognitive enhancers (Nootropics) used when trying to improve memory, intellect, and overall learning ability, second one is neuro-protective agents useful for protecting the brain from damage caused by stress, these drugs enhances mental resilience, as well as decreasing cognitive decline.^[4-6]

Figure 1: Functional Classification of *Medhya Rasayanas*.

The function of *Medha* is influenced by the balance of the three *Doshas*. The *Prana Vayu* provides the connection between *Buddhi* and *Manas*; while *Udana Vayu* allows for the expression of *Buddhi* through remembering past experiences. The *Sadhaka Pitta* is primarily responsible for the establishment of intelligence, decisiveness and clarity, etc. The *Kapha Dosha*, particularly *Tarpaka* and *Avalambaka Kapha*, provides stability, nourishment and balanced emotions to support *Dhriti*, thus preventing mental instability. This *Chikitsa* provides nourishment for the *Dhatu*s, strengthening *Agni*, purifying the *Srotas*, and increasing *Ojas*.^[5-7] The subsequent section of this article described specific psychological uses of *Medhya Rasayana*:

Mandukaparni

It has a bitter taste and a cooling effect, due to its *Laghu guna* it helps in *Deepana* & *Pachana*, facilitates *Srotoshodhana* process and boost up memory by virtue of its *Medha Guna*. Due to its cooling properties it has a positive effect on our *Tarpaka* and *Avalambaka Kapha*; that help to retain memory and offers *Mana Prasadana* effect. The chemical constituent components in *Mandukaparni* are saponins that are also protective to the brain and beneficial for behavioral problems. Many researchers believe that the cognitive enhancing effects of *Mandukaparni* relate to branching of nerve cells; this provides a solid basis for improvement in both learning and memory.

Yashtimadhu

It has *Medhya* effects primarily due to its *Prabhava*, it provides nourishment to *Mana* and *Buddhi*, also balances *Chala Guna* of *Vata dosha*. The main component of *Yashtimadhu* is to increase the availability of glucose to the brain, supports the brain's use of glucose to make energy, and has been shown to improve cognitive functioning. The anti-oxidant and acetylcholinesterase inhibiting effects of *Yashtimadhu* will also help to improve both memory and learning. *Yashtimadhu* plays an important role in reducing oxidative stress in neuronal tissues and improving overall brain function. The antioxidants present in *Yashtimadhu* help to protect neurons from oxidative damage by free radicals. *Yashtimadhu* helps in dementia and possess benefits in cognitive impairments.

Guduchi

Guduchi possesses *Ushna Virya*, alleviates *Tamas* and pacify vitiated *Kapha*. It stimulates *Pachaka Pitta* and optimizes *Agni*, ensuring *Indriyas* to receive proper nourishment. By balancing the *Sadhaka* and *Alochaka Pitta*, *Guduchi* improves *Buddhi* and *Medha*. *Guduchi* may enhance neuro-modulator release and promote dendrite growth within neurons. *Guduchi* also protects normal cognitive processes and boost overall psychological health.

Shankhapushpi

Shankhapushpi is a well-known *Medhya*; it offers neuro-protective, anti-stress and anti-anxiety properties. It provides improvements in *Chittodvega* and cognitive dysfunction. *Shankhapushpi* helps to balance the stress hormones of adrenaline and cortisol, thus helping to relax the body and improve mental clarity.^[7-9]

Suggested Mode of Action of Medhya Rasayanas

Medhya Rasayanas containing *Tikta Rasa*, *Laghu-Snigdha*, *Sheetha Virya* and *Madhura Vipaka* thus support *Medha*. *Medhya Rasayanas* work on a variety of levels from the neuro-physiological perspective: improving nutrition, increasing *Agni* and regulates circulation of *Srotas*. By modulating neurotransmitters and neurons, *Medhya Rasayanas* improve learning, memory and cognitive ability. In Ayurveda, *Kapha dosha* is responsible for impaired memory and intellect through its inherent qualities of dullness, while *Vata dosha* can also cause anxiety, instability, and uncertainty. *Medhya Rasayana* balances these two *Doshas* thus enhances memory retention, recall and cognitive function.^[8-10]

The modern scientific literature also confirms the effects of these herbs by demonstrating their ability to act on the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis as well as by normalizing the levels of neurotransmitters such as dopamine, serotonin and acetylcholine within the body, thereby improving overall mental function. *Medhya Rasayanas* improve learning ability, memory, and attention span through modulating the activity of cholinergic and GABAergic receptors. *Medhya Rasayanas* provide antioxidant protection to prevent oxidative stress, over-excitation, and loss of energy to neurons. These drugs enhance neuro-modulation by finding the optimal balance between excitatory and inhibitory neurotransmitters. Like modern nootropics,

Medhya Rasayanas act by modulating the availability of neuro-chemicals, enzymes and hormones to increase cerebral blood flow, improve oxygen delivery and therefore, support cognitive performance and enhance memory function through increased levels of acetylcholine and improved cerebral circulation.^[3,10]

CONCLUSION

There are many different ways that *Medhya Rasayana* can help improve brain function. Modern studies have found that these types of herbs can increase blood flow to the brain, increase balance and regulation of neurotransmitter levels, decrease neuro-inflammatory markers, stimulate new neuron formation, and prevent damage to neurons due to free radicals. By positively influencing certain pathways that contribute to behaviors, *Medhya Rasayana* can enhance ability to learn and improves overall mental performance. *Medhya Rasayana* enhances intellect by balancing the *Tridosha*. *Medhya Rasayana* influences *Rasa Dhatu* at the level of *Agni* and regulating digestion as well as metabolic processes. They also enhance the flow of *Rasa* through the micro-channels of circulation by clearing and opening the channels, thereby ensuring that brain receives adequate nutrition. Collectively, this action will strengthen *Dhi*, *Dhriti* and *Smriti*, thus improves mental functioning and prevent psychological illnesses.

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